

CONCEPTUAL BACKGROUND FOR THE USE OF

“EXTREME EVENT” AND RELATED TERMS, CONCEPTS, AND METHODS

WITHIN THE MAREXTREME MISSION

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GEFÖRDERT VOM

Conceptual background for the use of “extreme event” and related terms, concepts, and methods within the mareXtreme mission

With a changing climate and society, it is getting more important to develop a qualitative, mechanistic, and quantitative understanding of extreme events and their impacts in order to be able to address the risks to society and ecosystems. The interdisciplinary projects of the research mission mareXtreme contribute to enhancing this understanding by investigating different extreme events and their impacts on and interactions with coastal ecosystems, communities, and their activities. For this, a shared definition and conceptual framing of extreme events across scientific disciplines is essential to guide and harmonize the activities within mareXtreme.

The basis for the shared definition of extreme events outlined here centers around the concept of **risk**, defined by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) as the potential for adverse consequences for (coupled) human and/or ecological systems (IPCC, 2022). Risk has evolved as the central concept used by scientific communities working on climate change adaptation and disaster risk reduction. Risk results from dynamic interactions between **hazards** with (direct and indirect) **exposure(s)** and **vulnerabilities** of the affected human or ecological systems to the hazards (see glossary). With climate change and increasing societal exposure, risks for social and ecological systems increase, highlighting the need for adaptation and risk reduction measures (Pörtner et al., 2022).

When risks are realized, adverse **impacts** on ecosystems and/or societies can be observed (IPCC, 2022a). Besides direct impacts, cascading impacts exist where a hazard generates a sequence of secondary events in natural and human systems that result in physical, natural, social or economic disruption, whereby the resulting impact is significantly larger than the initial impact (IPCC, 2022a). Cascading impacts can also result from system interdependencies and their vulnerabilities. Furthermore, direct and cascading impacts can be a result of **responses** by risk management or adaptation to initial hazards, risks, or disasters (Hagenlocher et al., 2023; IPCC, 2022a; UNU-EHS & UNDRR, 2022).

When the realized consequences are so severe that they reflect highly significant and typically long-lasting consequences to society, the natural physical environment or ecosystems (Lavell et al., 2012) we speak of **extreme impacts**. Extreme impacts can be the outcome of a single extreme event, successive or compound extreme or non-extreme events, or the persistence of conditions (IPCC, 2022a; Lavell et al., 2012). Such conditions, factors, or events potentially affecting an element of society or ecosystems are also described as impact-drivers or climatic-impact drivers (CIDs) if the driver is directly related to the climate system (Ruane et al., 2022).

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Defining “extreme event”

Building on the understanding of IPCC’s Special Report on Extreme Events and Disasters (Lavell et al., 2012) and IPCC’s latest Assessment Report (AR6) (Pörtner et al., 2022) **an extreme event is defined within the mareXtreme mission as a hazard characterized by a change in physical/geological parameters below or above a defined threshold** (see Determining thresholds for extreme events). An extreme event can be hazardous with or without interaction with extreme environmental conditions and/or anthropogenic and natural drivers (Figure 1). It can be manifested as a singular event or can be the result of a sequence of events or a compound of multiple extreme or non-extreme events in an often complex interplay of drivers, impacts, and responses (Simpson et al., 2023). The change in physical/geological parameters can

- be a (climate-related or geological) hazard itself (e.g., the physical event of abnormally high sea surface temperature (SST) over a prolonged period = heatwave; a strong magnitude earthquake);
- lead to extreme biological, chemical, geological, or physical events that can trigger a hazard (e.g., marine heatwaves can lead to harmful algal blooms negatively affecting ecosystems, a volcanic sector collapse can cause a tsunami, storm surges can lead to extreme water levels and severe sea states that may lead to coastal erosion or flooding either by inundating the low elevation coastal zone (LE CZ) or by overtopping coastal protection infrastructure); or
- trigger hazards when interacting with anthropogenic and natural drivers affecting different parameters that accelerate the hazardous effect and shape the vulnerability and exposure to the hazard (e.g., high precipitation and river runoff in connection with constricted riverbeds leading to floods, low water levels in connection with high nutrient concentrations due to human activities leading to harmful algae blooms, a tsunami wave causing damage to a nuclear power plant leading to radiation leaks) (Figure 1).

To determine where and how impacts occur (e.g., direct or cascading impacts), mareXtreme investigates different elements of extreme events, ranging from marine geological, biological, and oceanographic hazards and their interaction with environmental conditions and anthropogenic and natural drivers, to understanding the factors that shape impacts on ecosystems and societies. This ability of mareXtreme to identify, study, and connect the key components of what makes a hazard “extreme” allows us to further our understanding and definition of the often widely used term “extreme events” into something that can be better addressed with targeted actions.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of the mareXtreme mission drawing on IPCC (IPCC, 2022; Pörtner et al., 2022). The framework illustrates the role of extreme events in driving risks and impacts within social-ecological systems. Extreme events are understood as a hazard. An extreme event can be the manifestation of a single event or the result of a sequence or compound of multiple events that trigger a change in physical/geological parameters below or above a defined threshold at a particular place and time which can be a hazard itself, lead to extreme biological, chemical, geological, or physical conditions that can trigger a hazard, or trigger hazards when interacting with anthropogenic and natural drivers that accelerate the hazardous effect and shape the vulnerability and exposure to the hazard. Besides the vulnerability and exposure of the system affected by the extreme event, the responses of the system shape the risk and influence the severity of the impact on ecosystems and society.

Determining thresholds for extreme events

As a wide range of physical and geological events in multiple contexts exists, also the thresholds that differentiate extreme events from more common events are manifold. Generally, the **thresholds account for the interacting qualifiers of intensity, frequency, duration, timing and/or spatial extent** (IPCC, 2023) of the physical/geological parameters that define the event. These qualifiers respectively describe the magnitude of the measurements above what is considered normal, how often the measurement exceeds that value, for how long it exceeds it, and when it happens and over which geographic area. Several of these qualifiers may have to be considered in the definition of an extreme event. For instance, to classify an increase in sea surface temperature (SST) as an extreme event referred to as a marine heatwave requires an increase in intensity exceeding a context-specific threshold for a duration of at least 5 days (Hobday et al., 2016). The relationships between different parameters or the occurrence of multiple sequenced or compound extreme events may also be considered when determining the thresholds. Where adequate, mareXtreme uses established thresholds. However, specific contexts exist that require the definition of their own thresholds or adopt concepts analogously. Depending on the impact, event type, and the associated physical/geological parameters, different quantitative methods exist to determine the thresholds and concepts. The selection of the quantitative method will also depend on available information, knowledge and data.

Using a **statistical distribution approach**, a value is commonly described as extreme if it is below or above a contextually meaningful percentile of values from a reference timeframe (which can be a day of the year, or a month). This approach is, for example, used in the case of marine heatwaves, where an SST value is considered extreme when it lies above the 90th percentile of seasonal values (Hobday et al., 2016).

Extreme value analysis, by comparison, is leveraged to define extreme events by extracting “extreme” values from the reference time series and determining their probability distribution (e.g., Coles, 2001). Commonly used criteria are values above a certain threshold based on expert knowledge or a block maximum such as the highest value of each year. The probability distribution can then be used to estimate the value of a parameter for a certain return period, e.g. the expected water level of a 100-year flood. For example, in the context of coastal flooding, a 200-year flood (0.005 exceedance probability) is defined as an extreme event and considered as a design parameter for coastal protection structures in Schleswig-Holstein (MELUR-SH, 2013).

These examples show that thresholds can differ depending on specific extreme events, systems, context, and the associated stakeholder values concerning the linked risks. Both approaches require a long-time series of reference values to investigate sub-seasonal phenomena. As with the selection of the approach, the required duration of the time series depends on the type of event and the context in which it may occur. An important consideration is the magnitude of non-extreme variability, including periodic changes (e.g. tidal water level or seasonal rainfall) and long-term trends (e.g. global warming or ocean acidification). For instance, sensitivity analyses showed that for the reliable definition of Marine Heat Waves typically 30 years of daily values are desired (Schlegel et al., 2019).

In contrast, in hydrography, it is assumed that a 30-year-long time series can only reliably derive return levels for 60 to 90-year periods, which is insufficient for planning protection against 100-year or 200-year floods (Klemes, 1993; Moran, 1957). If time series are too short, percentiles and probability distributions cannot be determined reliably. If the frequency of measurements is too low, gap-filling approaches might be used, however, this decreases the accuracy of the results.

As a result of climate change, it is expected that thresholds for extreme events will be crossed more frequently. Stemming from the fact that the assumption of stationarity - the very idea that natural systems fluctuate within an unchanging envelope of variability (Milly et al., 2008) - is no longer valid in a changing climate, e.g., recurrence intervals of extreme sea levels driven by storm surges become more common and frequent due to sea level rise. Formerly known centennial extremes receive higher probabilities of occurrence, while future centennial extremes under climate change get far more severe.

mareXtreme Glossary

This glossary is a living document and aims to create a (discussion and ultimately shared) understanding of concepts and terms that are relevant for the project.

The definitions in the table below are largely taken from/draw on the IPCC 6th Assessment Report (AR6 WG1: [Chapter 11.2.1 “Definition of Extremes”](#); AR6 WG2: Annex II - [Glossary](#)) and the IPCC Special Report on Extreme Events and disasters (SREX; [Chapter 1.2 “Extreme events, extreme impacts, and disasters”](#)).

[German summaries](#) of the reports can be found here: [Übersetzungen – de-IPCC](#). The glossary of the latest AR has not been translated (so far). However, the glossary of the AR5 should provide a good overview and understanding as well: [Klimaänderung 2013/2014 – Zusammenfassungen für politische Entscheidungsträger: Anhang \(de-ipcc.de\)](#).

Concept/term	Definition	Source	Examples	Characteristics	German term
Extreme event	<p>A hazard characterized by a change in physical/geological parameters below or above a defined threshold. An extreme event can be hazardous in or without interaction with extreme environmental conditions and/or anthropogenic and natural drivers. It can be manifested as a singular event or can be the result of a sequence of events or a compound of multiple extreme or non-extreme events in an often-complex interplay of drivers, impacts, and responses. The change in physical/geological parameters can</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • be a hazard itself; • lead to extreme biological chemical, geological, or physical events that can trigger a hazard; or • trigger hazards when interacting with anthropogenic and natural drivers affecting different parameters that accelerate the hazardous effect and shape the vulnerability and exposure to the hazard 	<p>Own drawing on IPCC SREX (IPCC, 2012b; Lavell et al., 2012) and IPCC AR6 WG2 (IPCC, 2022a; Pörtner et al., 2022)</p>	<p>Physical event of abnormally high sea surface temperature over a prolonged period = heatwave</p> <p>Excess river discharge leading to eutrophication and harmful algal blooms, storm surge leading to coastal floods</p> <p>High precipitation in connection with constricted riverbeds leading to floods</p> <p>Strong magnitude (Mw>9) earthquake</p>	Rare at a particular place and time	Extremereignis (IPCC, 2013/2014)
Hazard	The potential occurrence of a natural or human-induced physical event or trend that may cause loss of life, injury or other health impacts, as well as damage and loss to	IPCC AR6 WG2 (IPCC, 2022a, p. 2911)	Floods, droughts, storm surge, pollution, hypoxia, harmful algal blooms,	Slow (e.g. drought) vs sudden-onset (e.g. flash flood); single, compounding (e.g.	Gefährdung (IPCC, 2013/2014)

	property, infrastructure, livelihoods, service provision, ecosystems and environmental resources.		ground motion, lava flows, tsunami wave, etc.	drought & wildfire), concurring (flood during pandemic), cascading hazards (heavy rains leading to land slides); intensity/magnitude, onset, duration, extent, etc.	
Exposure	The presence of people; livelihoods; species or ecosystems; environmental functions, services, and resources; infrastructure; or economic, social, or cultural assets in places and settings that could be adversely affected [by a hazard/extreme climate event].	IPCC AR6 WG2 (IPCC, 2022a, p. 2908)	Infrastructure in a floodplain, ecosystems on a coastline, coastal communities	Varies in space and time; directly linked to a hazard (without potential hazard no exposure); can be direct (e.g. infrastructure in floodplains) or indirect (e.g. through cascading effects resulting from system interdependence)	Exposition (IPCC, 2013/2014)
Vulnerability	The propensity or predisposition to be adversely affected. Vulnerability encompasses a variety of concepts and elements, including sensitivity or susceptibility to harm and lack of capacity to cope and adapt.	IPCC AR6 WG2 (IPCC, 2022a, p. 2927)	Farmers practicing rainfed agriculture are more vulnerable to droughts than people with other livelihoods; lack of early warning systems increases vulnerability as people cannot anticipate impacts and prepare, etc.	Differential, dynamic, multi-dimensional	Verwundbarkeit/ Vulnerabilität (IPCC, 2013/2014)
Risk	“The potential for adverse consequences for human or ecological systems, recognising the diversity of values and objectives associated with such systems. [...] In the context of climate change impacts, risks result from dynamic interactions between climate-related hazards with the” exposure(s) and vulnerability/ies of the affected (coupled) human and/or ecological system(s) to the hazards.	IPCC AR6 WG2 (IPCC, 2022a, p.2921)	Risk of adverse consequences (impacts) on lives, livelihoods, health and well-being, economic, social and cultural assets and investments, infrastructure, services (including ecosystem services), ecosystems and species.	Differential, dynamic, complex (feedbacks, non-linearity, uncertainty, possible tipping points, cascading effects, response risks, etc.)	Risiko (IPCC, 2013/2014)

Response risk(s)	Risks linked to risk management and adaptation actions	IPCC AR6 WG2 (IPCC, 2022a)	“Reservoir effect” (overuse of reservoirs during droughts) Risks linked to “restriction measures” such as lockdowns during COVID-19	Measures aimed to reduce initial risk(s) can reinforce, re-distribute or create new risks	
Impact	<p>“The consequences of realised risks on natural and human systems, where risks result from the interactions of climate-related hazards (including extreme weather/climate events), exposure, and vulnerability. [...]</p> <p>Impacts may be referred to as consequences or outcomes, and can be adverse or beneficial.”</p>	IPCC AR6 WG2 (IPCC, 2022a, p.2912)	Impacts generally refer to effects on lives, livelihoods, health and well-being, ecosystems and species, economic, social and cultural assets, services (including ecosystem services) and infrastructure.	Impacts are the manifestation of risk(s); Can be adverse or beneficial; can be short and long-term, can be direct, indirect (cascading) or systemic	Folgen (Konsequenzen, Auswirkungen) (IPCC, 2013/2014)
Extreme impact	<p>“An extreme impact reflects highly significant and typically long-lasting consequences to society, the natural physical environment, or ecosystems. Extreme impacts can be the result of a single extreme event, successive extreme or non-extreme events, including non-climatic events (e.g., wildfire, followed by heavy rain leading to landslides and soil erosion), or simply the persistence of conditions, such as those that lead to drought [...].</p> <p>Whether an extreme event results in extreme impacts on humans and social systems depends on the degree of exposure and vulnerability to that extreme, in addition to the magnitude of the physical event”</p>	IPCC SREX (Lavell et al., 2012, p. 41-42)	Disaster signifies extreme impacts suffered by society (e.g. large-scale damage to infrastructure, loss of live)	<p>extreme impacts resulting from climate or geological, events / hazards can become disasters once they surpass thresholds in at least one of three dimensions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● spatial – so that damages cannot be easily restored from neighboring capacity; ● temporal – so that recovery becomes frustrated by further damages; ● intensity of impact on the affected population – thereby 	

				undermining, although not necessarily eliminating, the capacity of the society or community to repair itself	
Cascading impact	<p>“Cascading impacts from extreme weather/climate events occur when an extreme hazard generates a sequence of secondary events in natural and human systems that result in physical, natural, social or economic disruption, whereby the resulting impact is significantly larger than the initial impact.”</p> <p>Cascading impacts can also result from system interdependence and their vulnerabilities which can trigger impact cascades through systems. Furthermore, cascading impacts can be a result of (risk management or adaptation) responses to initial hazards, risks, or disasters</p>	<p>IPCC AR6 WG2 (IPCC 2022a, p. 2902)</p> <p>UNU-EHS & UNDRR, 2022; Hagenlocher et al., 2023</p>	Drought impacts on food insecurity, destroyed critical infrastructure as a result of one hazard leading to further consequences	Cascading impacts are complex and multi-dimensional, and are associated more with the magnitude of vulnerability than with that of the hazard; cascading impacts can also result from “responses” to hazards/disasters	Kaskadenartige Folgen (IPCC, 2022b)
Compound events	“the combination of multiple drivers and/or hazards that contributes to societal and/or environmental risk”	IPCC AR6 WG2 (IPCC 2022a, p. 2904)	Co-occurrence of drought and fire or earthquake and tsunami		<p>Zusammenhängende Ereignisse</p> <p>(Kombinierte Gefahren - compound hazards) (IPCC, 2012a)</p> <p>Ereignisbündel (Ratter et al., 2024)</p>
Adaptation	In human systems, the process of adjustment to actual or expected climate and its effects, in order to moderate harm or exploit beneficial	IPCC AR6 WG2 (IPCC 2022, p. 2898)	Restoring floodplains to give the river more space		Anpassung (IPCC, 2013/2014)

	<p>opportunities. In natural systems, the process of adjustment to actual climate and its effects; human intervention may facilitate adjustment to expected climate and its effects.</p>		<p>Reinforcing coastal infrastructures to protect from increasing storm surges</p> <p>Growing drought-resistant crops</p>		
<p>Residual risk</p>	<p>The risk related to climate change or geohazard impacts that remain following adaptation and mitigation efforts. Adaptation actions can redistribute risk and impacts, with increased risk and impacts in some areas or populations, and decreased risk and impacts on others.</p>	<p>IPCC AR6 WG2 (IPCC, 2022a, p.2920)</p>	<p>Manifests when design levels of, e.g., protection schemes are exceeded during, e.g., extreme events</p>	<p>Requires additional risk management strategies, e.g., risk layering approach</p>	

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